

Chloroplastic proteins are targets for the RipG effectors of *Ralstonia solanacearum*

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ABSTRACT

Ralstonia solanacearum type III effectors are necessary for disease development in host plant. A RipG type III effector family consisting of seven genes contains an F-box domain and leucine-rich repeats (LRRs). The F-box domain resembles eukaryotic F-box proteins, which form SCF ubiquitin ligase complex in combination with Skp1 and Cullin1 and control specific protein ubiquitination. RipG effectors are known to interact with Skp1-like protein in *Arabidopsis thaliana* through their F-box domains and hijack host SCF ubiquitin ligase complex. In this study, yeast two-hybrid screening was conducted to find out plant proteins interacting with the RipG effectors. The prey library was constructed using *Nicotiana benthamiana* and *Nicotiana tabacum* cDNA library. The bait plasmids were constructed with seven *ripG* genes of *R. solanacearum* OE1-1 strain. As a result, in addition to the previously reported Skp1, several chloroplastic proteins were found to interact with the RipG effectors, especially RipG2 and RipG7. While Skp1 bound to RipGs through the F-box domain, these chloroplastic proteins did not bind to the F-box domain but bound to either LRR or the N-terminal region. From these results, we hypothesize that chloroplastic proteins could be the targets for ubiquitination via RipG effectors.

1. Introduction

Ralstonia solanacearum is a devastating plant pathogen with a global distribution and invades an unusually wide host range, including economically important crops such as tomato, potato, tobacco, and eggplant (Hayward 1991; Genin and Denny 2012). The pathogen enters plant roots through natural openings or wounds, invades xylem vessels, proliferates and spreads into the whole vascular system. Cells produce extracellular polysaccharides, which block water transfer, resulting in wilting death of plant (Schell 2000).

Like other gram-negative phytopathogens, *R. solanacearum* possesses a type III secretion system (T3SS) and injects type III effectors (T3Es) directly into the host plant cells (Cornelis and van Gijsegem 2000; He et al. 2004). Bacterial T3Es contribute to disease development, although the mechanisms, by which each T3E functions inside plant cells, are not fully understood (Mudgett 2005; Peeters et al.

2013). The T3E AWR5 is an inhibitor of the TOR complex 1, which is a central regulator of eukaryotic cell growth in response to nutrient availability and stress conditions (Popa et al, 2016). The ChaC domain-containing effector RipAY exhibits γ -glutamyl cyclotransferase activity to degrade glutathione (Fujiwara et al. 2016). RipAW and RipAR show E3 ubiquitin ligase activity and significantly suppressed pattern-triggered immunity (Nakano et al. 2017).

A Japanese *R. solanacearum* strain OE1-1 is originally isolated from eggplant and pathogenic on both tobacco and tomato (Kanda et al. 2003). A draft genome sequence analysis reveals that there are more than 70 putative T3E genes in OE1-1 (unpublished data). Among them, a number of T3Es exist as multimember families based on function and sequence relatedness. A RipG (GALA) family T3E contains both an F-box domain and leucine-rich repeats (LRRs) (Cunnac et al. 2004) and interact with Skp1-like protein in *Arabidopsis thaliana* through F-box domain (Angot et al.

2006). The RipG F-box domain resembles eukaryotic F-box proteins, which form SCF-type E3 ubiquitin ligase in combination with Skp1 and Cullin1 and ubiquitinate a broad range of proteins (Kirkpatrick et al. 2005). Several reports indicate non-eukaryotic F-box proteins act by hijacking host SCF ubiquitin ligase complex for disease development (Tzfira et al. 2004; Angot et al. 2006; Baumberger et al. 2007). However, proteins targeted by the complex are still unknown. In this study, in order to find target proteins by the hijacked E3 ubiquitin ligase, we investigated the proteins that interact with RipG T3Es of *R. solanacearum* by using yeast two-hybrid (Y2H) screening.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Construction of a prey library

Total RNA was purified from leaves of *Nicotiana tabacum* or *Nicotiana benthamiana* using RNAiso plus (Takara). Mixture of leaves infected with *R. solanacearum* OE1-1 at 10^8 cfu mL⁻¹ for different periods of time and with no infection were used. After first strand cDNA synthesis, plant cDNA was fused to yeast GAL4 activating domain (AD) in pGADT7-Rec vector in Y187 yeast cells (Table 1) using Make Your Own “Make & Plate” Library System according to the manufacture’s instruction (Clontech). Yeast cells were spread on SD (synthetic defined) agar medium without leucine (SD/-Leu) to construct a prey library.

2.2. Preparation of bait plasmids

Seven *ripG* genes were PCR amplified and fused to yeast GAL4 DNA-binding domain (DNA-BD) in pGBKT7 vector (Clontech) with the in-fusion cloning method (Clontech). The vector pGBKT7 vector was linearized by primers, infusionA9 and infusionB9. Seven *ripG* genes, *ripG1*, *ripG2*, *ripG3*, *ripG4*, *ripG5*, *ripG6*, and *ripG7*, were amplified from OE1-1 genome DNA by pairs of primers (Table 2), OEP0914A3 and OEP0914B2, OEP0672A2 and OEP0672B2, OEP0028A2 and OEP0028B2, OEC1800A2 and OEC1800B2, OEC1801A2 and OEC1801B2, OEC1356A2 and OEC1356B2, OEC1357A2 and OEC1357B2, respectively, and cloned into pGBKT7 to construct pGBKP0914, pGBKP0672, pGBKP0028, pGBKC1800, pGBKC1801, pGBKC1356, and pGBKC1357, respectively. Y2HGold yeast cells (Table 1) were transformed with the recombinant plasmids and spread on SD agar medium without tryptophan (SD/-Trp).

2.3. Two-hybrid library screening using yeast mating

Screening was conducted according to the instruction of Matchmaker Gold Yeast-Two-Hybrid System (Clontech). Briefly, Y2HGold cells containing bait plasmids grown in SD/-Trp liquid media were mated with 1 ml of prey library cell suspension and then plated on the agar media of SD/-Trp/-Leu, referred as minimal media double dropouts (DDO), with aureobasidin A (DDO/A). Colonies appeared on these agar media were transferred on the agar media of SD/-Trp/-Leu/-adenine/-histidine, referred as minimal media quadruple dropouts (QDO), with aureobasidin A and X- α -Gal

(QDO/X/A) for a higher stringency selection to eliminate false positives. The prey plasmid was rescued from the blue colonies grown on QDO/X/A agar media.

2.4. Co-transformation with prey and bait plasmids

The protein screened by Y2H system was identified from *N. benthamiana* draft genome sequence v1.0.1 (Bombarely et al. 2012) and *N. tabacum* BX genome (Sierro et al. 2014) in Sol Genomics Network (<https://www.sgn.cornell.edu/>). The full length of cDNA was PCR amplified using plant cDNA as a template and pairs of primers (Table 2) and cloned into the linearized pGADT7 AD vector with the in-fusion cloning method. cDNA sequence for *N. benthamiana* SKP1-like protein 1A was found in Sequence ID Niben101Scf02378g02004.1. PCR product amplified with a pair of primers, Nb2004A1 and Nb2004B1, were cloned into linearized pGADT7 AD with infusionA11 and infusionB11, to construct pGADT7Nbskp1a. cDNA sequence for another SKP1-like protein 1A was found in Sequence ID Niben101Scf02658g00012.1. PCR product amplified with a pair of primers, Nb00012A1 and Nb00012B1, were cloned into pGADT7 AD, to construct pGADT7Nbskp1b. cDNA sequence for chloroplastic chlorophyll a-b binding protein 13 was found in Sequence ID Niben101Scf07510g00016.1. PCR product amplified with a pair of primers, Nb00016A1 and Nb00016B1, were cloned into pGADT7 AD, to construct pGADT7Nbcab13. cDNA sequence for chaperonin-like RbcX protein was found in Sequence ID Niben101Scf13231g02014.1. PCR product amplified with a pair of primers, Nb02014A1 and Nb02014B1, were cloned into pGADT7 AD, to construct pGADT7NbrbcX. cDNA sequence for chloroplastic ribulose biphosphate carboxylase small chain 8B was found in Sequence ID Niben101Scf01991g05015.1. PCR product amplified with a pair of primers, Nb05015A1 and Nb05015B1, were cloned into pGADT7 AD, to construct pGADT7NbrbcS. cDNA sequence for *N. tabacum* SKP1 was found in Sequence ID mRNA_2468. PCR product amplified with a pair of primers, Nt2488A1 and Nt2488B1, were cloned into pGADT7 AD, to construct pGADT7Ntskp1a. cDNA sequence for *N. tabacum* another SKP1 was found in Sequence ID mRNA_131316. PCR product amplified with a pair of primers, Nt131316A1 and Nt131316B1, were cloned into pGADT7 AD, to construct pGADT7Ntskp1b.

Two plasmids containing either the bait plant gene or the prey *ripG* gene were put into Y2HGold cells and plated on the DDO agar media. Transformants were grown in YPDA broth and spotted on the QDO/X/A agar media with series of dilutions, 10^{-1} , 10^{-2} and 10^{-3} .

2.5. Construction of domain deletion versions of RipG effectors

The F-box domain was deleted from RipG2. The F-box domain, LRR, and N-terminal region were deleted from RipG7. F-box deletion of *ripG2* was constructed as follows. Two fragments were amplified from pGBKP0672 by pairs of primers, OEP0672A2 and OEP0672B3, and OEP0672A3 and OEP0672B2, and mixed with linearized pGBKT7 to construct pGBKP0672dF. F-box deletion of *ripG7* was constructed as follows. Two fragments were amplified from

Table 1 Strains and plasmids used in this study

	Description	Reference
Strains		
<i>E. coli</i>		
DH12S	<i>araD139 Δ(ara-leu)7697 ΔlacX74 galU galK mcrA Δ(mrr-hsdRMS-mcrBC) rpsL deoR Ø80dlacZΔM15 nupG recA1/F9proAB1 lacI^q ZΔM15</i>	Invitrogen
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>		
Y187	<i>MATα, ura3-52, his3-200, ade2-101, trp1-901, leu2-3, 112, gal4Δ, gal80Δ, met⁻, URA3::GAL1_{UAS}-GAL1_{TATA}-lacZ, MEL1</i>	Clontech
Y2HGold	<i>MATα, trp1-901, leu2-3, 112, ura3-52, his3-200, gal4Δ, gal80Δ, LYS2::GAL1_{UAS}-GAL1_{TATA}-HIS3, GAL2_{UAS}-GAL2_{TATA}-ADE2, URA3::MEL1_{UAS}-MEL1_{TATA}-AUR1-C, MEL1</i>	Clontech
Plasmids		
pGBKT7	Yeast two-hybrid "bait" vector for expressing proteins fused to the GAL4 DNA-binding domain	Clontech
pGADT7 AD	Yeast two-hybrid "prey" vector for expressing proteins fused to the GAL4 activation domain	Clontech
pGADT7-Rec	Yeast vector for fusing a cDNA to the GAL4 activation domain by in vivo recombination	Clontech
pGBKP0914	<i>ripG1</i> on pGBKT7	This study
pGBKP0672	<i>ripG2</i> on pGBKT7	This study
pGBKP0028	<i>ripG3</i> on pGBKT7	This study
pGBKC1800	<i>ripG4</i> on pGBKT7	This study
pGBKC1801	<i>ripG5</i> on pGBKT7	This study
pGBKC1356	<i>ripG6</i> on pGBKT7	This study
pGBKC1357	<i>ripG7</i> on pGBKT7	This study
pGBKP0672dF	<i>ripG2</i> ΔF-box on pGBKT7	This study
pGBKC1357dF	<i>ripG7</i> ΔF-box on pGBKT7	This study
pGBKC1357dL	<i>ripG7</i> ΔLRR on pGBKT7	This study
pGBKC1357dN	<i>ripG7</i> ΔN-terminus on pGBKT7	This study
pGBKC1357N	N-terminal region of <i>ripG7</i> on pGBKT7	This study
pGBKC1357dBD	<i>ripG7</i> without BD on pGBKT7	This study
pGBKNbskp1a	<i>Nbskp1a</i> on pGNKT7	This study
pGBKNbskp1a-ripG7	<i>Nbskp1a</i> and <i>ripG7</i> without BD on pGBKT7	This study
pGADNbskp1a	<i>Nbskp1a</i> on pGADT7 AD	This study
pGADNbskp1b	<i>Nbskp1b</i> on pGADT7 AD	This study
pGADNtskp1a	<i>Ntskp1a</i> on pGADT7 AD	This study
pGADNtskp1b	<i>Ntskp1b</i> on pGADT7 AD	This study
pGADNbcab13	<i>Nbcab13</i> on pGADT7 AD	This study
pGADNbrbcX	<i>NbrbcX</i> on pGADT7 AD	This study
pGADNbrbcS	<i>NbrbcS</i> on pGADT7 AD	This study

Table 2 Primers used in this study

Name	Sequence (5'-3')	Gene
for ripG cloning		
OEP0914A3	gaggccgaattcccATGGGAAACCAGTTTTTCGAT	<i>ripG1</i>
OEP0914B2	aggtcgacggatcccCGGCGCGGGGCGATC	
OEP0672A2	gaggccgaattcccTTGCGGCTGGGGCCCGC	<i>ripG2</i>
OEP0672B2	aggtcgacggatcccCAGAACGGTCCCGCAGCG	
OEP0672A3	gccgacTGGGACAAGGCGGCATTC	<i>ripG2</i>
OEP0672B3	ttgtccaCGTCGGCTGTGTTGCCTC	Fbox deletion
OEP0672A4	gcgctaccgcegtcgGGCGAGGCGGGCGCG	<i>ripG2</i>
OEP0672B4	CGACGGCGGTAGCGCGCG	LRR deletion
OEP0028A2	gaggccgaattcccATGGCTCCGCCATCCATGC	<i>ripG3</i>
OEP0028B2	aggtcgacggatcccGCGAGGATGCCCTGGCAC	
OEC1800A2	gaggccgaattcccATGGGATAACCAGTTCTGGGC	<i>ripG4</i>
OEC1800B2	aggtcgacggatcccGGGCCCGATGGCGGTGC	
OEC1801A2	gaggccgaattcccGTGAAACCTGTCGCTCCGGT	<i>ripG5</i>
OEC1801B2	aggtcgacggatcccCGGCAAACCTCACCGGCATG	
OEC1356A2	gaggccgaattcccATGGTGTGCGGCATTCCAC	<i>ripG6</i>
OEC1356B2	aggtcgacggatcccGCACCTCAAGCACACGTCAC	
OEC1357A2	gaggccgaattcccATGATGTTCAAGCGCATCGA	<i>ripG7</i>
OEC1357B2	aggtcgacggatcccCGCCAAGGCAAACAGTGC	
OEC1357A3	tcgaggagAACAAGGCGATGCTCGGC	<i>ripG7</i>
OEC1357B3	gcctgttCTCCTCGATATTCCGCAC	Fbox deletion
OEC1357A7	gcatcgAATACGCGCATCAAGGGCAC	<i>ripG7</i>
OEC1357B7	cgctattGCGATGCAGTTGGCCGAGC	LRR deletion
OEC1357A9	cccgatCGGAATATCGAGGAGATGC	<i>ripG7</i>
OEC1357B91	atattccgCATCGGGAATTCGGCCTC	N-terminal deletion
OEC1357A10	caagcctctgaaagATGATGTTCAAGCGCATCGA	
OEC1357B11	aggtcgacggatcccCTCCTCGATATTCCGCAC	<i>ripG7</i> N-terminal cloning
For plant cDNA cloning		
Nb2004A1	agtgaattccaccgTCGTCCTCTAAGATGATCG	<i>Nbskp1a</i>
Nb2004B1	gtctcgatgccaccTCACTCAAATGCCCAAGCA	
Nb2004A2	gaggccgaattcccTCGTCCTCTAAGATGATCG	<i>Nbskp1a</i>
Nb2004B2	aggtcgacggatcccTCACTCAAATGCCCAAGCA	
Nb00012A1	agtgaattccaccgAAGATGATCGTGCTAAGGAG	<i>Nbskp1b</i>
Nb00012B1	gtctcgatgccaccTCACTCGAAGGCCAGGC	
Nb00016A1	agtgaattccaccgGCATCAATGGCAGCAAC	<i>Nbcab13</i>
Nb00016B1	gtctcgatgccaccTTAAGATCCAGGAACAAACT	
Nb02014A1	agtgaattccaccgGTGGGAACTATATTTGGGAC	<i>NbrbcX</i>
Nb02014B1	gtctcgatgccaccTCAATCCAAACTTCCAGCA	
Nb05015A1	agtgaattccaccgGCTTCCTCAGTTATGTCTT	<i>NbrbcS</i>
Nb05015B1	gtctcgatgccaccTTAGTAGCCTTCTGGCTTG	
Nt2488A1	agtgaattccaccgAAGATGATCGTATTGAGGAG	<i>Ntskp1a</i>
Nt2488B1	gtctcgatgccaccTCACTCAAAGGCCAAGC	
Nt131316A1	agtgaattccaccgTCTACTTCAAAAATGATTGT	<i>Ntskp1b</i>
Nt131316B1	gtctcgatgccaccTCACTCAAAGGCCAG	
For linearizing vector		
infusionA9	gggatccgtcgacctgacg	linearize pGBKT7
infusionB9	cgggaattcggcctccatg	
infusionA11	ggtgggcatcgatacggga	linearize pGADT7 AD
infusionB11	cgggtggaattcactggc	
infusionB12	ctttcaggacgcttgcctcaag	linearize pGBKT7 with A9
infusionA13	ggcgtaatcatggtcatagc	linearize pGBKT7
infusionB13	aagcttgcacgcccgtagag	
pGBKA1	ccggcatgcaagcttGGGCTCTTCGCTATTACG	amplify from pGBKT7
pGBKB1	gacatgattacgccTGAATTGTGAGCGGATAAC	

Table 3 Y2H-screened proteins interacting with RipG effectors

	<i>N. tabacum</i>	<i>N. benthamiana</i>
RipG1	<i>Skp1</i>	<i>Skp1</i>
RipG2	<i>Skp1</i> Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase Cathepsin B-like cysteine proteinase Protein phosphatase 2C family protein	ATP synthase subunit b Chlorophyll a-b binding protein 13 Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase Ribulose biphosphate carboxylase small chain 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate oxidase homolog
RipG3	None	None
RipG4	None	None
RipG5	<i>Skp1</i>	<i>Skp1</i>
RipG6	<i>Skp1</i>	<i>Skp1</i>
RipG7	ATP synthase subunit b Chlorophyll a-b binding protein 7 branched-chain amino acid transaminase 5 NADPH quinone oxidoreductase chain 4 Photosystem I reaction center subunit II Phototropin 2 Glutathione S transferase ATP synthase subunit d, mitochondrial-like	<i>Skp1</i> ATP synthase subunit b Chlorophyll a-b binding protein 13 Oxygen-evolving enhancer protein 1 Chaperonin-like RbcX protein

Chloroplastic proteins are shown in bold. Skp1 is listed in italics.

pGBKC1357 by pairs of primers, OEC1357A2 and OEC1352B3, and OEC1357A3 and OEC1357B2, and mixed with linearized pGBKT7 to construct pGBKC1357dF. About 8-kb fragment was amplified from pGBKC1357 by OEC1357A7 and OEC1357B7 and ligated by in-fusion, to construct pGBKC1357dL deleting LRR from *ripG7*. About 9-kb fragment was amplified from pGBKC1357 by OEC1357A9 and OEC1357B9 and ligated by in-fusion, to construct pGBKC1357dN deleting N-terminus from *ripG7*.

About 400-bp N-terminal region of *ripG7* was amplified by OEC1357A2 and OEC1357B11 (Table 2) and cloned into pGBKT7, to construct pGBKC1357N.

2.6. Construction of a plasmid for yeast three-hybrid system

The *N. benthamiana skp1* gene *Nbskp1a* was cloned into pGBKT7, to construct pGBKNbskp1a. The *gal4* BD domain was deleted from pGBKT7. The *ripG7* gene was cloned into this modified vector, to construct pGBKC1357dBD. DNA fragment containing *ripG7* on pGBKC1357dBD was inserted into pGBKNbskp1a, to construct pGBKNbskp1a-*ripG7*. This plasmid contains both *Nbskp1a* fused to BD domain and *ripG7*. pGBKT7 was linearized by primers, infusionA9 and infusionB12, which deleted *gal4* BD domain. PCR-amplified *ripG7* by OEC1357A10 and OEC1357B2 was in-fusion cloned into this linearized pGBKT7, to construct pGBKC1357dBD. *Nbskp1a* was amplified from pGADNbskp1a by a pair of primers Nb2004A2 and Nb2004B2, and cloned into pGBKT7, construct pGBKNbskp1a. This pGBKNbskp1a was linearized by infusionA13 and infusionB13. DNA fragment containing *ripG7* was amplified from pGBKC1357dBD by pGBKA1 and pGBKB1, and cloned into linearized pGBKNbskp1a, to construct pGBKNbskp1a-*ripG7*. This plasmid contains both *Nbskp1a* fused to BD domain and *ripG7*.

3. Results

3.1. RipG effectors interacted with tobacco Skp1 proteins

Tobacco Skp1s of both *N. benthamiana* and *N. tabacum* were observed to interact with RipG effectors, RipG1, RipG2, RipG5, RipG6, and RipG7. No proteins were screened with RipG3 and RipG4 (Table 3). This is consistent with a previous finding that groups of *Arabidopsis* Skp1 interact with RipG effectors (Angot et al. 2006). Full lengths of *skp1* cDNA, *Nbskp1a*, *Nbskp1b*, *Ntskp1a*, and *Ntskp1b*, were amplified from mRNAs of *N. benthamiana* and *N. tabacum* and cloned into the prey expression pGADT7 AD vector. All four Skp1s interacted well with RipG effectors except RipG3 and RipG4 (Fig. 1).

3.2. RipG effectors interacted with several plant proteins rather than Skp1

We found that several tobacco proteins rather than Skp1 interacted with RipG effectors, especially RipG2 and RipG7 (Table 3). Identified plant proteins were quite diverse and did not seem to have the shared characteristics. When we carefully looked at the predicted destination of these proteins, most of them turned out to be chloroplastic proteins, which are encoded in the nucleus (Table 3, shown in bold). Among the identified plant proteins, we cloned the full lengths of cDNAs of chlorophyll a-b binding protein 13, chaperonin-like RbcX protein, and ribulose biphosphate carboxylase small chain from *N. benthamiana* mRNA, Nbcab13, NbrbcX, and NbrbcS, respectively, into the prey expression pGADT7 AD vector. All three chloroplastic proteins interacted well with RipG2 and RipG7 (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1 Interaction of RipG effectors with tobacco Skp1 proteins in yeast. Each of seven *ripG* genes was fused to GAL4 DNA-binding domain in pGBKT7 vector. Full lengths of *N. benthamiana* cDNA of (A) NbSkp1a, (B) NbSkp1b, (C) NtSkp1a, and (D) NtSkp1b were fused to GAL4 activating domain in pGADT7 AD vector. Two plasmids containing either the prey *ripG* gene or the bait plant *skp1* gene were put into Y2HGold cells. Transformants were grown in YPDA broth and spotted on the QDO/X/A agar media with series of dilutions, 10^{-1} , 10^{-2} and 10^{-3} . Interaction positive clones turned blue by catalyzing X- α -Gal. in pGADT7 AD.

3.3. Identification of binding site of RipG2 to chloroplastic protein

RipG2 contains the F-box domain in the middle and two LRR domains on both N- and C-termini (Fig. 3A). We constructed the F-box deletion derivative of RipG2, RipG2dF. NbSkp1 did not interact with RipG2 when the F-box domain was deleted (Fig. 3B), which is good agreement with the previous data (Angot et al. 2006). Instead, the chloroplastic protein NbCab13 did bind to RipG2dF even with higher affinity (Fig. 3B). These results indicate that Skp1 and chloroplastic proteins do not share the binding site on RipG2.

3.4. Identification of binding sites of RipG7 to chloroplastic proteins

RipG7 contains the F-box domain and one LRR domain on C-terminus (Fig. 4A). NbSkp1 did not interact with the F-box deletion derivative, RipG7dF, as observed with RipG2 (Fig. 4B). All three chloroplastic proteins, NbRbcX, NbCab13, and NbRbcS, interacted with RipG7 even if the F-box domain was deleted (Fig. 5). In order to find out the binding site of the chloroplastic proteins to RipG7, we constructed LRR-deleted and N-terminal deleted versions of RipG7, RipG7dL and RipG7dN, respectively (Fig. 4A). NbSkp1 interacted with these two derivatives (Fig. 4B). On the contrary, NbRbcX lost interaction with RipG7 when LRRs was deleted (Fig 5), indicating that NbRbcX binds to RipG7 through LRRs. While both NbCab13 and NbRbcS interacted with RipG7dL, no bindings were observed with RipG7dN (Fig. 5B and 5C), indicating that binding site of RipG7 to NbCab13 and NbRbcS is the N-terminal region. Indeed, NbRbcS interacted with N-terminal region of RipG7 (Fig. 4A and 5C).

3.5. Simultaneous binding of NbSkp1 and NbRbcX to RipG7

Yeast three-hybrid assay was performed to investigate if both NbSkp1 and NbRbcX could interact with RipG7 at the same time. NbSkp1 did not directly interact with NbRbcX (Fig. 6). When RipG7 existed together with NbRbcX fused to GAL4-AD and NbSkp1 fused to GAL4-BD, yeast cells turned blue (Fig. 6). This result clearly indicates that NbSkp1 and NbRbcX simultaneously bind to RipG7.

4. Discussion

The RipG effectors of *R. solanacearum* possess the F-box domain and LRRs, both of which are important for protein-protein interactions. The F-box protein is a component of SCF (Skp1, Cullin1, F-box proteins) ubiquitin ligase complex, which controls polyubiquitination of target proteins for degradation by 26S proteasome (Lechner et al. 2006). Although F-box proteins and 26S proteasome system are originally found in eukaryotic cells, F-box-like effector proteins have been described in both plant and animal pathogens (Magori and Citovsky 2011; Price et al. 2009). These non-eukaryotic F-box proteins act by hijacking their host SCF ubiquitin ligases to interfere with their host ubiquitin/proteasome pathway (Angot et al. 2006), although proteins targeted by the complex are still unknown. In this study, we found that RipG effectors, especially RipG2 and ripG7, interact with chloroplastic proteins of *N. tabacum* and *N. benthamiana*. We speculate that SCF^{RipG} complex interacting Skp1 with RipG effectors would target the plant chloroplastic proteins for ubiquitination and subsequent degradation.

Fig. 2 Interaction of RipG effectors with three *N. benthamiana* chloroplastic proteins in yeast. Each of seven *ripG* genes was fused to GAL4 DNA-binding domain in pGBKT7 vector. Full lengths of *N. benthamiana* cDNA of (A) NbCab13 (chlorophyll a-b binding protein 13), (B) NbRbcX (chaperonin-like RbcX protein), and (C) NbRbcS (ribulose biphosphate carboxylase small chain 8B) were fused to GAL4 activating domain in pGADT7 AD vector. Two plasmids containing either the prey *ripG* gene or the bait plant gene were put into Y2HGold cells. Transformants were grown in YPDA broth and spotted on the QDO/X/A agar media with series of dilutions, 10^{-1} , 10^{-2} and 10^{-3} . Positive protein-protein interaction was evaluated as indicated in Fig. 1

Fig. 3 Interaction of RipG2 deletion derivatives with *N. benthamiana* proteins in yeast. (A) Schematic structure of RipG2. RipG2dF represents the deletion of the F-box domain of RipG2. LRR indicates the Leucine Rich repeat. (B) Y2HGold cells were co-transformed with *ripG2* derivatives in PGBKT7 and either *Nbskp1* or *Nbcab13* in pGADT7 AD. Positive protein-protein interaction was evaluated as indicated in Fig. 1

Fig. 4 Interaction of RipG7 deletion derivatives with NbSskp1 in yeast. (A) Schematic structure of RipG7. RipG7dF, RipG7dL, and RipG7dN deleted the F-box domain, the LRRs domain, and the N-terminal region, respectively. RipG7-N contains the N-terminal region fused to GAL4 DNA-binding domain. (B) Y2HGold cells were co-transformed with *ripG7* derivatives in PGBKT7 and *Nbskp1* in pGADT7 AD. Positive protein-protein interaction was evaluated as indicated in Fig. 1

Fig. 5 Interaction of RipG7 deletion derivatives with chloroplastic proteins in yeast. Y2HGold cells were co-transformed with ripG7 derivatives in PGBKT7 and (A) NbrbcX, (B) Nbcab13, and (C) NbrbcS in pGADT7 AD. Positive protein-protein interaction was evaluated as indicated in Fig. 1. RipG7dF, RipG7dL, and RipG7dN represent deletion of the F-box domain, the LRRs domain, and the N-terminal region, respectively. RipG7-N contains the N-terminal region fused to GAL4 DNA-binding domain

Several studies on photosynthesis and plant defense have shown that photosynthesis rates decrease locally after treatment with phytopathogens (Bonfig et al. 2006). It is unclear that such decreases are the consequence of the plant defense or the pathogens aggressively decrease the photosynthesis (Bolton 2009). Both of *rbcS* and *cab* transcripts are reduced more than 20-fold in barley leaves challenged with powdery mildew (Swarbrick et al. 2006). In order to survive and spread in the plant, *R. solanacearum* might control the photosynthetic activity by degrading the chloroplastic proteins through SCF^{GALA} complex. So, it is tempting to speculate that *R. solanacearum* RipG effectors

target the chloroplastic proteins of host plants to inhibit photosynthesis and impair plant immunity for disease development.

Fig. 6 Yeast three-hybrid assay. RipG7, NbSkp1-BD and RipG7+Nbskp1-BD contain *ripG7* fused to GAL4 DNA-binding domain, *Nbskp1a* fused to GAL4 DNA-binding domain and both of *ripG7* alone and *Nbskp1a* fused to GAL4 DNA-binding domain, respectively, in PGBKT7. Each of the plasmid transformed Y2HGold cells containing *NbrbcX* fused to GAL4 activating domain in pGADT7 AD. Cells were concentrated 10 times in colonies shown as 10

One of the chloroplastic proteins NbRbcX bound to RipG7 through LRRs. We verified that NbSkp1 bound to RipG7 at the same time. LRR of RipG effectors belong to Cysteine-Containing LRR (CC-LRR) subfamily of plant, animal and fungi proteins (Kajava et al. 2008). Based on the selective evolutionary pressure acting on RipG proteins, it is hypothesized that the convex surface of the LRR domains might be the binding site of ligand protein relevant to the adaptor function of the F-box RipG proteins. NbRbcX could be the ligand for ubiquitination. Two other proteins, NbCab13 and NbRbcS, bound to the N-terminal region instead of the LRR domain. No significant domain structures are observed in the N-terminal region of RipG7. Nucleus-encoded chloroplastic proteins contain chloroplast transit peptides that act as chloroplast targeting sequences (Bruce 2000). Although at a primary structural level, transit peptide sequences are highly divergent in length, composition and organization, transit peptides are suggested to contain multiple domains for direct interaction with envelope lipids, chloroplast receptors and the stromal processing peptidase. The N-terminal region of RipG7 could mimic either of domains for binding to chloroplastic proteins.

While 5 RipG effectors interacted with Skp1, only RipG2 and RipG7 interacted with chloroplastic proteins. Among 7 RipG effectors, RipG5 and RipG7 belong to the core T3Es, which are conserved in almost all *R. solanacearum* strains and estimated to probably present in the ancestral *R. solanacearum* strain (Peeters et al. 2013). A strong likelihood of positive selection is proposed to act on *ripG7* (Remigi et al. 2011). Furthermore, RipG7 is an essential host-specificity factor on *Medicago truncatula* (Angot et al. 2006). All together, RipG7 could function as a main effector in the RipG family.

5. Conclusion

R. solanacearum T3E, RipG2 and RipG7, are F-box proteins and interact with Skp1 to hijack the host SCF ubiquitin ligase complex. We demonstrated that the hijacked ubiquitin ligase complex might target the chloroplastic proteins to reduce the chloroplast activity.

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